

COMMUNICATIVE DIALOGUE IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BUILDING THEIR SKILLS

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'qituvchining muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish vositalari muloqot madaniyatining tarbiyalovchi imkoniyatlarini ro'yobga chiqarish ko'p jihatdan o'qituvchining shaxsiy sifatlari bilan belgilanishini ta'kidlab o'tilishi ularning asosiy faoliyati o'qituvchining o'quvchilar bilan bo'ladigan muloqot madaniyati individual uslublarini shakllantirish o'qituvchi o'zining xushmuomalaligi, madaniyati, go'zal xulqi, muloqotda o'quvchilar qalbiga yo'l topa olishi bilan o'z mahoratini namoyish qilib, muloqot madaniyatining tashkiliy shakllariga ijtimoiy-psixologik jarayonlari haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kishilik jamiyati, etnopsixologik, o'qituvchi, pedagogik muloqot, psixologik muloqot, siyosiy, dunyoqarash, kasbiy layoqat, kasbiy madaniyat, ilk tarbiyaviy faoliyati.

Annotation: In this article, it is emphasized that the means of forming the communication culture of the teacher, the realization of the educational potential of the communication culture is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher, their main activity is the communication between the teacher and the students. the formation of individual styles of culture, the teacher demonstrated his skills with his politeness, culture, good manners, his ability to find a way to the hearts of students in communication, and the social-psychological processes of organizational forms of communication culture were discussed. .

Key words: personal society, ethnopsychological, teacher, pedagogy communication, psychological communication, political, worldview, professional ability, professional culture, early educational activities.

Аннотация: В данной статье подчеркивается, что средства формирования культуры общения учителя, реализация воспитательного потенциала культуры общения во многом определяются личностными качествами учителя, основной его деятельностью является общение между учителем и учениками. Формирование индивидуальных стилей культуры, педагог продемонстрировал свои умения вежливостью, культурностью, хорошими манерами, умением находить путь к сердцам учащихся в общении, а также обсуждались социально-психологические процессы организационных форм культуры общения.

Ключевые слова: личностное общество, этнопсихологический, педагог, педагогическое общение, психологическое общение, политическое, мировоззрение, профессиональные способности, профессиональная культура, ранняя образовательная деятельность.

The problem of forming a culture of communication in the teacher's professional activity is solved based on the needs and requirements of the individual society. Therefore, in the current period, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" does not limit itself to motivations for choosing a profession, professional training, professional ability and professional skills, but also to create a professional culture in the personal activities of future pedagogues. It is emphasized that it is absolutely necessary. In our republic, various scientific researches have been conducted in different eras regarding the unique ethnopsychological qualities of the teaching profession, feelings, abilities, working methods, ways of acquiring the secrets of pedagogical skills, and the culture of interpersonal communication. It should be emphasized that it is determined by the teacher's personal qualities in many ways. The method of pedagogical communication culture, which is chosen correctly in all respects, corresponds to the spiritual level of the teacher, unique characteristics, helps to solve the following set of tasks: first, special attention to each student in communication and

harmony with the class team simplifies the general communication process, prepares the ground for the teacher's free pedagogical activity, easily resolves conflict situations;

secondly, organizing interaction with a student on the basis of free communication, choosing pedagogical and psychological communication methods appropriate to their age characteristics, opens the way to know his psyche, to "enter" his inner world;

thirdly. the moral and ethical norms of the teacher in pedagogical communication are the key to success, increase the effectiveness of education, ensure the teacher's satisfaction and peace of mind in all stages of communication. The methodology of formation of individual styles of communication culture of the teacher with students includes the following stages:

In order to improve their professional skills, young teachers who are just starting their pedagogical activity should regularly work on forming a culture of communication with students.

In organizing the educational process, the culture of pedagogical dialogue is a force that directs the direct interaction of teachers and students towards a certain goal. At this point, it is important to note that the teacher should take into account the following situations:

- the teacher's adherence to the culture of communication from the very first educational activities, in this process planning the daily interaction with the teacher and the group of students depending on the situation, paying attention to every action, the tone of words, the most traditional communication acquire good qualities;

recording various situations in the class team based on communication, students to compare his/her behavior with the previous state and the state after the educational activity; analyze the results of his/her communication style from a critical point of view and continuously eliminate the shortcomings.

Creating the necessary words, pleasant tone of voice, behavior;

- it is not enough to know its conditions for the effective development of the culture of pedagogical communication, it is necessary to start interaction with students in the tradition of "teacher-student" and solve important tasks based on mutual exchange of ideas. to attract the attention of the subject; what should be understood by the object of communication, that is, to attract the attention of the reader? This means that the teacher demonstrates his skills with his politeness, culture, good manners, and the ability to find a way to the hearts of students in communication, and the organizational form of communication culture.

It is based on social and psychological basis. A young teacher who adheres to the culture of pedagogical communication, which is a unique quality of professional activity, should embody the following characteristics:

- a socially-politically active person with high spiritual views, strong and stable faith, loyalty to the ideals of our state, national idea and ideology of independence, feelings of patriotism and self-sacrifice, corresponding to the socio-political demands and needs of our country;

- the formation of sincere love for students, the ability to understand all their needs, interests, motives of behavior, behavior;

- Pedagogical observation of events occurring in society, events occurring in the world, nature, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, inter-national relations, the ability to strive for innovation, creative research;

- rational understanding of the characteristics of people's behavior and relationships in all aspects of pedagogical activity, forming a reflexive attitude towards one's own activity;

to react rationally and intelligently to any emergency situations, news happening in the society, and social and economic changes, to be able to set the right goals for oneself, to make a plan, able to directly control, manage and demonstrate their capabilities;

demonstrate the ability to organize and manage public actions in pedagogical activities, temporary group relations in the public system; the breadth of the worldview and scope of thinking, the wide interest in worldly knowledge, the aptitude for scientific research, the regular improvement of certain scientific potential and the level of pedagogical skills; possessing mysterious power, armed with methods of psychological influence.

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